

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory
4901 Hawkins NE
Albuquerque, NM 87109
TEL: 505-345-3975 FAX: 505-345-4107
Website: www.hallenvironmental.com

March 09, 2020

Michael Jones

National Cave and Karst Research Institute
400-1 Cascades Ave
Carlsbad, NM 88220
TEL: (830) 312-8131
FAX:

RE: San Solomon Springs

OrderNo.: 2002C53

Dear Michael Jones:

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory received 1 sample(s) on 2/25/2020 for the analyses presented in the following report.

These were analyzed according to EPA procedures or equivalent. To access our accredited tests please go to www.hallenvironmental.com or the state specific web sites. In order to properly interpret your results, it is imperative that you review this report in its entirety. See the sample checklist and/or the Chain of Custody for information regarding the sample receipt temperature and preservation. Data qualifiers or a narrative will be provided if the sample analysis or analytical quality control parameters require a flag. When necessary, data qualifiers are provided on both the sample analysis report and the QC summary report, both sections should be reviewed. All samples are reported, as received, unless otherwise indicated. Lab measurement of analytes considered field parameters that require analysis within 15 minutes of sampling such as pH and residual chlorine are qualified as being analyzed outside of the recommended holding time.

Please don't hesitate to contact HEAL for any additional information or clarifications.

ADHS Cert #AZ0682 -- NMED-DWB Cert #NM9425 -- NMED-Micro Cert #NM0901

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Andy Freeman', is written over a light blue horizontal line.

Andy Freeman
Laboratory Manager
4901 Hawkins NE
Albuquerque, NM 87109

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

Analytical Report

Lab Order 2002C53

Date Reported: 3/9/2020

CLIENT: National Cave and Karst Research Institut

Client Sample ID: GS-1

Project: San Solomon Springs

Collection Date: 2/24/2020 11:00:00 AM

Lab ID: 2002C53-001

Matrix: AQUEOUS

Received Date: 2/25/2020 9:18:00 AM

Analyses	Result	RL	Qual	Units	DF	Date Analyzed	Batch
EPA METHOD 8015M/D: DIESEL RANGE							Analyst: CLP
Diesel Range Organics (DRO)	ND	1.0		mg/L	1	2/29/2020 2:39:49 AM	50767
Motor Oil Range Organics (MRO)	ND	5.0		mg/L	1	2/29/2020 2:39:49 AM	50767
Surr: DNOP	111	70-130		%Rec	1	2/29/2020 2:39:49 AM	50767
EPA METHOD 8015D: GASOLINE RANGE							Analyst: NSB
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	ND	0.050		mg/L	1	3/2/2020 9:42:47 PM	G66962
Surr: BFB	83.5	67.5-110		%Rec	1	3/2/2020 9:42:47 PM	G66962
EPA METHOD 8270C: PAHS							Analyst: JDC
Naphthalene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
1-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
2-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Acenaphthylene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Acenaphthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Fluorene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Phenanthrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Anthracene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Fluoranthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Pyrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Benz(a)anthracene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Chrysene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Benzo(a)pyrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Surr: N-hexadecane	65.0	48.1-106		%Rec	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	70.2	43.3-97.7		%Rec	1	3/5/2020 11:13:20 AM	50778

Refer to the QC Summary report and sample login checklist for flagged QC data and preservation information.

Qualifiers:	*	Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.	B	Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
	D	Sample Diluted Due to Matrix	E	Value above quantitation range
	H	Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded	J	Analyte detected below quantitation limits
	ND	Not Detected at the Reporting Limit	P	Sample pH Not In Range
	PQL	Practical Quantitative Limit	RL	Reporting Limit
	S	% Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix		

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2002C53

09-Mar-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute

Project: San Solomon Springs

Sample ID: MB-50725	SampType: MBLK	TestCode: EPA Method 8015M/D: Diesel Range								
Client ID: PBW	Batch ID: 50725	RunNo: 66883								
Prep Date: 2/27/2020	Analysis Date: 2/28/2020	SeqNo: 2300706			Units: %Rec					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Surr: DNOP	1.0		1.000		100	70	130			

Sample ID: LCS-50725	SampType: LCS	TestCode: EPA Method 8015M/D: Diesel Range								
Client ID: LCSW	Batch ID: 50725	RunNo: 66883								
Prep Date: 2/27/2020	Analysis Date: 2/28/2020	SeqNo: 2300707			Units: %Rec					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Surr: DNOP	0.53		0.5000		106	70	130			

Sample ID: MB-50767	SampType: MBLK	TestCode: EPA Method 8015M/D: Diesel Range								
Client ID: PBW	Batch ID: 50767	RunNo: 66883								
Prep Date: 2/28/2020	Analysis Date: 2/28/2020	SeqNo: 2302467			Units: mg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Diesel Range Organics (DRO)	ND	1.0								
Motor Oil Range Organics (MRO)	ND	5.0								
Surr: DNOP	1.1		1.000		112	70	130			

Sample ID: LCS-50767	SampType: LCS	TestCode: EPA Method 8015M/D: Diesel Range								
Client ID: LCSW	Batch ID: 50767	RunNo: 66883								
Prep Date: 2/28/2020	Analysis Date: 2/28/2020	SeqNo: 2302468			Units: mg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Diesel Range Organics (DRO)	5.2	1.0	5.000	0	104	70	130			
Surr: DNOP	0.52		0.5000		104	70	130			

Qualifiers:

* Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix

B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
E Value above quantitation range
J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
P Sample pH Not In Range
RL Reporting Limit

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2002C53

09-Mar-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute
Project: San Solomon Springs

Sample ID: b1	SampType: MBLK		TestCode: EPA Method 8015D: Gasoline Range							
Client ID: PBW	Batch ID: G66962		RunNo: 66962							
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 3/2/2020		SeqNo: 2303531		Units: mg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	ND	0.050								
Surr: BFB	17		20.00		86.8	67.5	110			

Sample ID: 2.5UG GRO LCS	SampType: LCS		TestCode: EPA Method 8015D: Gasoline Range							
Client ID: LCSW	Batch ID: G66962		RunNo: 66962							
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 3/2/2020		SeqNo: 2303532		Units: mg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	0.47	0.050	0.5000	0	93.6	70.8	121			
Surr: BFB	18		20.00		89.8	67.5	110			

Sample ID: 2002c53-001ams	SampType: MS		TestCode: EPA Method 8015D: Gasoline Range							
Client ID: GS-1	Batch ID: G66962		RunNo: 66962							
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 3/2/2020		SeqNo: 2303539		Units: mg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	0.43	0.050	0.5000	0	86.2	51.1	131			
Surr: BFB	19		20.00		96.3	67.5	110			

Sample ID: 2002c53-001amsd	SampType: MSD		TestCode: EPA Method 8015D: Gasoline Range							
Client ID: GS-1	Batch ID: G66962		RunNo: 66962							
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 3/2/2020		SeqNo: 2303541		Units: mg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	0.42	0.050	0.5000	0	83.1	51.1	131	3.59	20	
Surr: BFB	19		20.00		97.0	67.5	110	0	0	

Qualifiers:

- * Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
- D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
- H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
- ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
- PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
- S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix
- B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
- E Value above quantitation range
- J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
- P Sample pH Not In Range
- RL Reporting Limit

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2002C53

09-Mar-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute

Project: San Solomon Springs

Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Sample ID: mb-50778 SampType: MBLK TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs Client ID: PBW Batch ID: 50778 RunNo: 67058 Prep Date: 3/2/2020 Analysis Date: 3/5/2020 SeqNo: 2308192 Units: µg/L										
Naphthalene	ND	0.50								
1-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50								
2-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50								
Acenaphthylene	ND	0.50								
Acenaphthene	ND	0.50								
Fluorene	ND	0.50								
Phenanthrene	ND	0.50								
Anthracene	ND	0.50								
Fluoranthene	ND	0.50								
Pyrene	ND	0.50								
Benz(a)anthracene	ND	0.50								
Chrysene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(a)pyrene	ND	0.50								
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	ND	0.50								
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	ND	0.50								
Surr: N-hexadecane	58		87.60		66.2	48.1	106			
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	15		20.00		73.7	43.3	97.7			

Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Sample ID: ics-50778 SampType: LCS TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs Client ID: LCSW Batch ID: 50778 RunNo: 67058 Prep Date: 3/2/2020 Analysis Date: 3/5/2020 SeqNo: 2308193 Units: µg/L										
Naphthalene	13	0.50	20.00	0	63.3	41.8	97.8			
1-Methylnaphthalene	13	0.50	20.00	0	62.7	44.7	104			
2-Methylnaphthalene	11	0.50	20.00	0	56.4	45	101			
Acenaphthylene	13	0.50	20.00	0	64.8	51.2	102			
Acenaphthene	14	0.50	20.00	0	70.4	53.2	101			
Fluorene	14	0.50	20.00	0	68.8	57.6	106			
Phenanthrene	14	0.50	20.00	0	72.3	57.6	109			
Anthracene	14	0.50	20.00	0	71.1	56.1	98.9			
Fluoranthene	15	0.50	20.00	0	76.1	61.4	114			
Pyrene	14	0.50	20.00	0	71.9	58	110			
Benz(a)anthracene	14	0.50	20.00	0	70.0	60	102			
Chrysene	12	0.50	20.00	0	60.1	50.8	93.4			
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	15	0.50	20.00	0	76.4	56.2	118			

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- ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
- PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
- S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix

- B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
- E Value above quantitation range
- J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
- P Sample pH Not In Range
- RL Reporting Limit

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2002C53

09-Mar-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute

Project: San Solomon Springs

Sample ID: Ics-50778		SampType: LCS		TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs						
Client ID: LCSW		Batch ID: 50778		RunNo: 67058						
Prep Date: 3/2/2020		Analysis Date: 3/5/2020		SeqNo: 2308193			Units: µg/L			
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	14	0.50	20.00	0	70.7	57.7	119			
Benzo(a)pyrene	14	0.50	20.00	0	72.1	55.5	114			
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	15	0.50	20.00	0	74.4	53	110			
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	15	0.50	20.00	0	76.3	55	113			
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	15	0.50	20.00	0	73.4	51.2	115			
Surr: N-hexadecane	63		87.60		71.5	48.1	106			
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	16		20.00		79.5	43.3	97.7			

Sample ID: Icsd-50778		SampType: LCSD		TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs						
Client ID: LCSS02		Batch ID: 50778		RunNo: 67058						
Prep Date: 3/2/2020		Analysis Date: 3/5/2020		SeqNo: 2308194			Units: µg/L			
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Naphthalene	14	0.50	20.00	0	70.0	41.8	97.8	10.1	25.4	
1-Methylnaphthalene	14	0.50	20.00	0	71.9	44.7	104	13.7	21.5	
2-Methylnaphthalene	14	0.50	20.00	0	70.0	45	101	21.5	25.2	
Acenaphthylene	14	0.50	20.00	0	71.7	51.2	102	10.1	30.3	
Acenaphthene	16	0.50	20.00	0	78.7	53.2	101	11.1	28.1	
Fluorene	15	0.50	20.00	0	76.4	57.6	106	10.5	33	
Phenanthrene	16	0.50	20.00	0	82.3	57.6	109	12.9	24.5	
Anthracene	16	0.50	20.00	0	81.6	56.1	98.9	13.8	26.9	
Fluoranthene	17	0.50	20.00	0	87.4	61.4	114	13.8	21.8	
Pyrene	16	0.50	20.00	0	78.6	58	110	8.90	27	
Benzo(a)anthracene	16	0.50	20.00	0	79.4	60	102	12.6	27.4	
Chrysene	13	0.50	20.00	0	67.2	50.8	93.4	11.2	20.4	
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	17	0.50	20.00	0	84.6	56.2	118	10.2	22.5	
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	16	0.50	20.00	0	80.8	57.7	119	13.3	24.1	
Benzo(a)pyrene	16	0.50	20.00	0	82.5	55.5	114	13.4	27.3	
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	17	0.50	20.00	0	82.7	53	110	10.6	18.5	
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	17	0.50	20.00	0	84.7	55	113	10.4	28.4	
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	17	0.50	20.00	0	84.3	51.2	115	13.8	21.8	
Surr: N-hexadecane	68		87.60		78.1	48.1	106	0	0	
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	17		20.00		84.0	43.3	97.7	0	0	

Qualifiers:

* Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
 D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
 H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
 ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
 PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
 S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix

B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
 E Value above quantitation range
 J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
 P Sample pH Not In Range
 RL Reporting Limit

Sample Log-In Check List

Client Name: **NATIONAL CAVE AND K**

Work Order Number: **2002C53**

RcptNo: **1**

Received By: *Juan Rojas* **2/25/2020 9:18:00 AM**
 Completed By: *Juan Rojas* **2/28/2020 11:50**
 Reviewed By: *JR 2/28/20*

Chain of Custody

1. Is Chain of Custody sufficiently complete? Yes No Not Present
 2. How was the sample delivered? UPS

Log In

3. Was an attempt made to cool the samples? Yes No NA
 4. Were all samples received at a temperature of >0° C to 6.0°C Yes No NA
 5. Sample(s) in proper container(s)? Yes No
 6. Sufficient sample volume for indicated test(s)? Yes No
 7. Are samples (except VOA and ONG) properly preserved? Yes No
 8. Was preservative added to bottles? Yes No NA
 9. Received at least 1 vial with headspace <1/4" for AQ VOA? Yes No NA
 10. Were any sample containers received broken? Yes No
 11. Does paperwork match bottle labels? Yes No
 (Note discrepancies on chain of custody)
 12. Are matrices correctly identified on Chain of Custody? Yes No
 13. Is it clear what analyses were requested? Yes No
 14. Were all holding times able to be met? Yes No
 (If no, notify customer for authorization.)

of preserved bottles checked for pH: _____
 (<2 or >12 unless noted)
 Adjusted? _____
 Checked by: *V62/28/20*

Special Handling (if applicable)

15. Was client notified of all discrepancies with this order? Yes No NA

Person Notified:	<input type="text"/>	Date:	<input type="text"/>
By Whom:	<input type="text"/>	Via:	<input type="checkbox"/> eMail <input type="checkbox"/> Phone <input type="checkbox"/> Fax <input type="checkbox"/> In Person
Regarding:	<input type="text"/>		
Client Instructions:	<input type="text"/>		

16. Additional remarks:

17. Cooler Information

Cooler No	Temp °C	Condition	Seal Intact	Seal No	Seal Date	Signed By
1	0.8	Good				

Chain-of-Custody Record

Client: NCK&E

Mailing Address: 400-1 Casades

Ave Carlsbad, NM

Phone #: 505-312-8131

email or Fax#: mjames@nckri.com

QA/QC Package: Standard Level 4 (Full Validation)

Accreditation: Az Compliance

NELAC Other

EDD (Type)

Turn-Around Time:

Standard Rush

Project Name:

San Solomon Springs

d 2/15

Project #:

Project Manager:

Michael Jones

d 2/15

Sampler:

On Ice: Yes No

of Coolers: 1

Cooler Temp (including CF): 0.9-0.1 = 0.5 (°C)

Container Type and #

Preservative Type

HEAL No.

1L sample glass

250ml Amber glass

40ml HD

40ml HCl

Date

Time

Matrix

Sample Name

2/24/2020 11:00

11:00

11:00

11:00

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Date:

Time:

Relinquished by:

Michael Jones

Date:

Time:

Relinquished by:

Michael Jones

Date:

Time:

Via:

Date:

HALL ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS LABORATORY

www.hallenvironmental.com

4901 Hawkins NE - Albuquerque, NM 87109

Tel. 505-345-3975 Fax 505-345-4107

Analysis Request

BTEX / MTBE / TMB's (8021)	TPH:8015D(GRO / DRO / MRO)	8081 Pesticides/8082 PCB's	EDB (Method 504.1)	PAHs by 8310 or (8270SIMS)	RCRA 8 Metals	Cl, F, Br, NO ₃ , NO ₂ , PO ₄ , SO ₄	8260 (VOA)	8270 (Semi-VOA)	Total Coliform (Present/Absent)
	X			X					

Remarks:

Received by: Michael Jones Date: 2/24/2020 Time: 11:00

If necessary, samples submitted to Hall Environmental may be subcontracted to other accredited laboratories. This serves as notice of this possibility. Any sub-contracted data will be clearly notated on the analytical report.